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Material reflection/transmission losses and permittivity/conductivity estimation from 2 GHz up to 260 GHz

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Summary

The academic and industrial research communities are proposing for the new 6G wireless communication system a radio interface operating at sub-THz frequencies above 100 GHz due to the wide unused available bandwidth in the sub-THz spectrum. A channel model valid from a few GHz to a few hundred GHz is required to assess the performance of such systems and compare them with current wireless systems operating at centimeter or millimeter waves. This paper presents material reflection-transmission coefficients and permittivity-conductivity results continuously between 2 GHz and 260 GHz. It aims to extend the current knowledge on wave-material interaction and make the link between below and above 100 GHz frequencies. Twenty-two different building materials commonly used in an indoor environment such as plasterboard, concrete, glass or wood are measured. The measurement setup is a normal incidence free space setup based on a vector network analyzer with optional millimeter wave extension modules connected at frequencies above 50 GHz. Measurement results are compared to simulations using the ITU model P.2040-3 and an ITU-like model where the ITU model theoretical approach is kept but the permittivity and conductivity are fitted by measurements. Measurements agree the ITU-fitted model for most of the materials up to 60 GHz. Rough surfaces and heterogeneous materials explain differences between the model and measurements that are generally equal to a few dB but exceeds 10 dB for some materials

1. Introduction

In the last decade, research on the fifth generation (5G) radio systems led to the exploration of millimeter wave (mmW) frequencies up to 100 GHz to achieve higher data rate performance than 4G [1]. Nowadays, the academic and industrial research communities are proposing for the new 6G wireless communication system [2][3][4][5] a radio interface operating at terahertz frequencies due to the wide unused available bandwidth in the THz spectrum [7][8][9] [10]. More specifically, the sub-terahertz band (sub-THz), representing frequencies from 100 GHz to 300 GHz, is of particular interest for the low atmospheric absorption and rain attenuation compared to above 300 GHz frequencies [11]. As a general rule, the performance evaluation of wireless communication systems requires dedicated propagation channels that are calibrated on targeted frequencies, which would imply to perform measurement between 100 GHz and 300 GHz for 6G. Nevertheless, the current RF component limitations [3][7][10] (amplifier, antenna array, etc) and the high free space loss above 100 GHz raises the question of the sub-THz 6G system competitiveness compared to mmW 5G systems. Sub-THz 6G wireless system will certainly be compared to previous systems and a frequency consistent propagation channel from a few GHz to a few hundred GHz is required to perform a fair comparison between those systems.

Physical models such as ray tracing or ray launching are frequently proposed for system performance evaluation [12][13][14][15]. They used a geographical database that describes accurately the environment around various simulation points such transmitters, receivers, RIS, relays, etc. All possible paths (direct, reflected, diffracted, diffused paths) between two or more simulation points can be consistently generated. The path amplitude is given by physical laws according to the interaction type between the electromagnetic (EM) wave and the environment. For instance, the direct path amplitude is given by the well-known free space loss equation, the diffracted path amplitude is given either by the knife-edge diffraction theory or by the Uniform Theory of Diffraction/General Theory of Diffraction (UTD/GTD) [16]. The reflected or transmitted path amplitude is given by Fresnel equations. Compared to losses due to other physical phenomena, reflection and transmission losses depend on two material dielectric coefficients, the permittivity and conductivity, that may be frequency dependent. A physical model shall include a material table indicating with a theoretical approach the material permittivity and conductivity or indicating with a more pragmatical approach the transmission and reflection losses. Whatever the approach, the frequency dependency of these parameters shall be specified from a few GHz to 300 GHz as it was pointed hereabove for the 6G performance evaluation.

Papers providing material transmission/reflection losses or permittivity/conductivity estimations are summarized in Table 1. The list mainly targeted recent contributions addressing mmW and sub-THz frequencies. This list is consequently not exhaustive but enough representative to highlight the following observations. Measurements are either performed for specific frequencies or limited frequency ranges, either above or below 100 GHz. Comparing results for a material at frequency A in a paper A with results at frequency B in a paper B do not allow to conclude on the frequency impact as the observed differences between the two papers may not come from the frequency but from different materials used in paper A and paper B even if this material is labelled identically in both papers. The provided literature review shows a lack of studies addressing all frequencies in a continuous way from the cmW up the sub-THz frequency domain. Regarding standardized model, many physical simulations refer to the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) recommendation P.2040 [49] that specifies characteristics of building materials and structures affecting the EM wave propagation. The ITU model is specified up to 100 GHz and may not be valid for 6G simulations where sub-THz frequencies up to 300 GHz are considered

The presented work aims to conduct a consistent frequency-dependency analysis of material transmission and reflection losses based on frequency continuous measurements from 2 GHz up to 260 GHz. The ITU model will also be compared on the measurement and its validity above 100 GHz will be discussed. Compared to results presented in previous contributions from the same authors, this work includes measurements up to 260 GHz instead of 170 GHz, new materials, the permittivity and conductivity estimation and the ITU model validity discussion.

The deliverable is organized as follows. Section II presents EM wave theories to compute reflection/transmission losses and introduces the ITU model. Section III describes the equipment, the measurement procedure, the selected materials and the post-processing method. The permittivity/conductivity estimation methods are explained in section IV. Measurements are compared to an ITU-like model fitted by measurements in section V. The validity of the ITU model and its possible extensions above 100 GHz is discussed in section VI.

Table 1: Literature review on material characterization campaign. R and/or T loss means that the paper contains information on the reflection (R) and/or transmission coefficients (T). ϵ_r/σ means that the paper contains information on the relative permittivity and/or conductivity. Frequencies in brackets indicates a continuous frequency scan.

Ref.	Institution	Frequency (GHz)	Material type	Parameters
[17]	Univ. Braunschweig, Germany	[100-500]	Plaster, white paint, glass	R/T loss, ϵ_r
[18]	Univ. Oulu, Finland	[100-2000]	Plastic, paper, hard board, glass	R/T loss, ϵ_r
[19]	Univ. Braunschweig, Germany	[100-1000]	Wood, glass, plastic, brick	T loss, ϵ_r
[20]	Univ Surrey, Guildford, UK	[500-750]	Glass, plasterboard, concrete, plywood, MDF, plastic	R loss
[21]	Chiba Instit. of Tech., Japan	[200-500]	Glass, concrete, granite	ϵ_r, σ
[22]	Chiba Instit. of Tech., Japan	[200-500]	Glass	ϵ_r, σ
[23]	Chiba Instit. of Tech., Japan	[220-320]	Glass	T/R loss
[24]	ETRI, Daejeon, Korea	253	Concrete, wood	R loss
[25]	Univ. Michigan	1, 240	Wool, polyester, acrylic, cotton	ϵ_r, σ
[26]	NC Univ., Raleigh, USA	28, 39, 120, 144	Glass, plywood, drywall, ceiling tile	R/T loss
[27]	Univ Gent, Belgium	[110-170]	Wood, cardboard, tabletop, acrylic, PVC	R/T loss
[28]	Ericsson, Gothenburg, Sweden	28, 140	Drywall, wood	R/T loss
[29]	Univ. Bochum, Germany	[60-330]	Plasterboard, aerated concrete, concrete, brick, sandstone, ceramic	T loss
[30]	Aalto univ., Espoo, Finland	[0.6 – 95]	standard/coated/laminated glass	T loss
[31]	Boise Univ., USA	28, 73, 91	Plywood, ceiling tile, glass, drywall, concrete	T loss
[32]	Univ Bologna/Carthage, Italia/Spain	10, 30, 60, 100, 300 not for all materials	Brick, teflon, paraffin, chipboard, sandstone, plaster, marble, plywood, wood, nylon, granite	ϵ_r/σ
[33]	New York Univ, USA	140	Glass, drywall	T loss
[34]	New York Univ, USA	28	Glass, drywall, concrete	T/R loss
[35]	New York Univ, USA	28, 73, 140	Glass, drywall	T/R loss
[36]	Univ. Durham, UK	28, 39	Glass, Plexiglas, hardboard, plasterboard, wood, MDF	T/R loss
[37]	Facebook	28, 60	Glass, concrete	T/R loss
[38]	Univ. Zagreb, Croatia	[26-40]	Glass, concrete, plasterboard, acrylic, chipboard, wood	T loss
[39]	North China Univ., Beijing, China	28, 39	Wood, glass	T loss
[40]	Univ. Sheffield/Durham, U.K.	39	Wall	R/T loss, ϵ_r/σ
[41]	Chongqing Univ., China	[40-50]	Granite, marble, PVC, wood	T/R loss, ϵ_r/σ
[42]	Univ. Aalborg, Denmark	[0.1-67]	20 Materials	ϵ_r/σ
[43]	Huawei, China	[2-74]	Glass, laminated glass, wood	T loss
[44]	Aalto Univ., Espoo, Finland	60	Plasterboard, plywood, glass, concrete	ϵ_r
[45]	Interdigital, USA	60	Cinder block, brick, drywall, plexiglass, wood, ceiling tile	ϵ_r/σ
[46]	Univ. Vigo, Spain	from 5 to 62	Literature review: brick, concrete, plasterboard, glass, plywood and chipwood,	ϵ_r
This	Orange Labs Belfort, France	[2-260]	22 Materials	R/T loss, ϵ_r/σ

2. Wave-material interaction modelling

This section reminds basic equations that describe the interaction between EM waves and homogeneous isotropic non-magnetic materials. These equations are then applied to compute the transmission and reflection losses of a material slab.

2.1. Transmission and reflection losses for lossy dielectrics

The fundamental Maxwell's equations can be rewritten in (1) in order to model the EM wave propagation in a dielectric. For sake of simplicity, only equations for the electric field are given as the magnetic field respects the same equations.

$$\Delta \vec{E} = \mu_0 \varepsilon_0 \varepsilon_r \frac{\partial^2 \vec{E}}{\partial t^2} + \mu_0 \sigma \frac{\partial \vec{E}}{\partial t} \quad (1)$$

μ_0 and ε_0 are the vacuum permeability and permittivity, respectively. ε_r and σ are the dielectric relative permittivity and conductivity, respectively. By assuming a sinusoidal wave with angular frequency ω , equation (1) can be simplified as given by (2)

$$\Delta \vec{E} = -(\mu_0 \varepsilon_0 \varepsilon_r \omega^2 - j \mu_0 \sigma \omega) \vec{E} = -\gamma^2 \vec{E} \quad (2)$$

with γ being the propagation constant.

Considering a plane wave polarized in direction z and travelling in the x direction, the solution of the wave equation (2) is given by (3). Directions x and z are perpendicular.

$$\vec{E}(x, t) = E_0 e^{j\omega t - \gamma x} \vec{e}_z = E_0 e^{j(\omega t - \beta x)} e^{-\alpha x} \vec{e}_z \quad (3)$$

E_0 is the electric field amplitude, α and β are the attenuation and phase constants given by (4) and (5), respectively

$$\alpha = \omega \sqrt{\frac{\mu_0 \varepsilon_0 \varepsilon_r}{2}} \sqrt{\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{\sigma}{\omega \varepsilon_0 \varepsilon_r}\right)^2} - 1} \quad (4)$$

$$\beta = \omega \sqrt{\frac{\mu_0 \varepsilon_0 \varepsilon_r}{2}} \sqrt{\sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{\sigma}{\omega \varepsilon_0 \varepsilon_r}\right)^2} + 1} \quad (5)$$

In usual indoor environments, EM waves may be affected by propagation either through metallic materials, air or building constructions such as concrete, glass, wood, etc. The metallic material conductivity is very high, implying a very high attenuation constant. Consequently, a good approximation is to consider that the EM wave cannot propagate through metallic objects. The relative air permittivity is close to 1 and the air conductivity is very small. Consequently, propagation through the air is considered as the same as propagation in the vacuum with a relative permittivity and conductivity equal to 1 and 0, respectively. With these conditions, α is null and β is equal to $\omega \sqrt{\mu_0 \varepsilon_0}$ or ω/c , with C being the wave celerity in vacuum. Equation (3) can be rewritten in (6).

$$\vec{E}(x, t) = E_0 e^{j\left(\omega t - \frac{\omega}{c}x\right)} \vec{e}_z = E_0 e^{j\left(\omega t - \frac{2\pi x}{\lambda}\right)} \vec{e}_z \quad (6)$$

with λ being the wavelength in vacuum.

Building materials may be considered as low loss dielectrics with $(\sigma/\omega \varepsilon_0 \varepsilon_r)^2 \ll 1$. Under this condition, α and β can be approximated by $\frac{\sigma}{2} \sqrt{\frac{\mu_0}{\varepsilon_0 \varepsilon_r}}$ and $\omega \sqrt{\mu_0 \varepsilon_0 \varepsilon_r}$, respectively. The wave propagation speed v is then equal to $C/\sqrt{\varepsilon_r}$ and equation (3) can be rewritten as in (7)

$$\vec{E}(x, t) = E_0 e^{j(\omega t - \frac{\omega}{c} \sqrt{\epsilon_r} x)} e^{-\frac{\sigma}{2} \sqrt{\frac{\mu_0}{\epsilon_0 \epsilon_r}} x} \vec{e}_z \quad (7)$$

When the EM wave encounters an interface between two dielectrics having different relative permittivity ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 , a fraction of the wave is reflected, and another part is transmitted at the interface level. Let's denote by \vec{E}_i , \vec{E}_r , and \vec{E}_t the incident, reflected and transmitted fields at normal incidence, respectively. r and t are the reflection and transmission coefficients such that $\vec{E}_r = r\vec{E}_i$ and $\vec{E}_t = t\vec{E}_i$. According to Fresnel equations, r and t are defined by (8) and (9) respectively.

$$r = \frac{\sqrt{\epsilon_1} - \sqrt{\epsilon_2}}{\sqrt{\epsilon_1} + \sqrt{\epsilon_2}} \quad (8)$$

$$t = \frac{2\sqrt{\epsilon_1}}{\sqrt{\epsilon_1} + \sqrt{\epsilon_2}} \quad (9)$$

2.2. Application to a material slab

Let's consider a material slab with thickness d and coefficients (ϵ_r, σ) surrounded by air as shown in Figure 1. This configuration is very common in human environment. It may be a glass window, concrete wall, plasterboard partition wall, etc. This configuration is the experimental configuration described in the next section as well. r and t are the reflection and transmission coefficients at the air-material interface with $r = \frac{1 - \sqrt{\epsilon_r}}{1 + \sqrt{\epsilon_r}}$ and $t = \frac{2}{1 + \sqrt{\epsilon_r}}$. p is the penetration loss inside the material. The air and material relative permittivity are 1 ($\epsilon_1 = 1$) and ϵ_r ($\epsilon_2 = \epsilon_r$) respectively

Figure 1: Reflection and transmission coefficients in a lossy dielectric slab at a normal incidence

Figure 1 illustrates the different paths created by the interaction between the EM wave and the slab. As the propagating wave reaches the first material interface, a part of the signal is reflected, and the rest is transmitted through the material. The transmitted part from the first material interface penetrates through the material, and it is attenuated due to the penetration loss. Arriving to the second interface, a part of the signal will be transmitted, and the rest will be reflected. Likewise, multiple reflections are created inside the slab. In the following, for the sake of simplicity, only transmitted paths 1 and 2 (named 1T and 2T) and reflected paths 1 and 2 (named 1R, 2R) will be considered, as illustrated in Figure 1. We denote $H_r^{Mod}(f)$ and $H_t^{Mod}(f)$ the frequency-dependent reflection and transmission transfer functions (TF) of the material slab. $H_r^{Mod}(f)$ and $H_t^{Mod}(f)$ are expressed as $H_r^{Mod}(f) = r - \sqrt{\epsilon_r} t^2 p^2 r$ and $H_t^{Mod}(f) = \sqrt{\epsilon_r} t^2 p - \sqrt{\epsilon_r} t^2 p^3 r^2$. Here, r and t are the reflection and transmission TF at the air-dielectric interface. r , t , ϵ_r and σ are potentially frequency-dependent, but for clarity reasons, it does not appear in the equations. The ITU-R recommendation [49] proposes a constant permittivity value regardless the frequency and formulates the frequency-dependent conductivity σ as $\sigma = cf^d$, f being expressed in GHz. ϵ_r , c and d are given for some materials such as plasterboard or glass. $H_r^{ITU}(f)$ and $H_t^{ITU}(f)$ are $H_r^{Mod}(f)$ and $H_t^{Mod}(f)$ applying the ITU model. $H_t^{ITU}(f)$ and $H_r^{ITU}(f)$ power profiles are illustrated in Figure 2 for the glass ($d = 8 \text{ mm}$, $\epsilon_r = 6.25$, $\sigma =$

$0.0043f^{1.19}$) and the plasterboard ($d = 13 \text{ mm}$, $\epsilon_r = 1.99$, $\sigma = 0.0116f^{0.708}$). A *pp* prefix added to H functions indicates the power profile of H functions with $pp_H(f) = 10 * \log_{10}(|H(f)|^2)$.

Figure 2: $pp_H_r^{ITU}(f)$ and $pp_H_t^{ITU}(f)$ for glass

Figure 2 illustrates the permittivity and conductivity impact of the reflection and transmission TF. We also observe the small-scale effects created by the interferences between the multipath created inside the slab. Due to the penetration loss increase with the frequency, small-scale effects tend to become less relevant at high frequencies

As a first approach, the discussion about the ITU model validity above 100 GHz may be divided in two sub-discussions. The first sub-discussion is about the validity of the ITU theoretical framework. For instance, does the permittivity remain constant and is the conductivity modelled by cf^d ? Are the conductivity and permittivity still relevant parameters to compute reflection and transmission losses? The second sub-discussion is about the numerical values of ϵ_r , c and d . Shall they be updated to correctly represent reflection and transmission losses? An ITU-like model was defined to help the analysis related to the first sub-discussion. This model is called ITUF and keeps the same theoretical approach of the ITU model but parameters ϵ_r , c and d are fitted on measurement presented in this paper. We define $H_r^{ITUF}(f)$ and $H_t^{ITUF}(f)$ the transfer functions $H_r^{Mod}(f)$ and $H_t^{Mod}(f)$ applying the ITUF model.

3. Measurement setup and procedure

3.1. Measurement equipment

The measurement equipment, illustrated in Figure 3, is a normal incidence free space measurement system based on a Vector Network Analyzer (VNA). S11 and S21 parameters are measured contiguously from 2 to 260 GHz in order to process material transmission and reflection losses at normal incidence. The free space measurement technique is used in the conducted study since it allows measurements up to the sub-THz frequency range with usual building material samples.

Figure 3: Schematic overview of the VNA based measurement system

Frequency band	VNA	Frequency extenders	Antenna	Gain
2 - 30 GHz	R&S ZVA-40	No	Dual ridge horns SH2000	6 - 15 dB
30 - 50 GHz	Keysight PNA-67		Flann Microwave horns 23240-25	25 dB
50 - 75 GHz	R&S ZVA-40	OML WR15	Flann Microwave horns 25240-20	20 dB
75- 110 GHz		OML WR10	Flann Microwave horns 27240-20	20 dB
110 - 170 GHz		VDI WR6.5	Millitech horns SGH-06	25 dB
170 - 260 GHz		VDI WR4.3	Millitech horns SGH-04	25 dB

Table 2 : Measured frequency sub-bands with the appropriate equipment

Two VNAs (4 ports Rohde & Schwarz ZVA 40, and Keysight PNA 67) were used to cover a frequency band from 2 GHz up to 260 GHz. Measurements were divided in contiguous sub-bands that were defined depending on the used equipment limitations. Table 2 illustrates all the measured sub-bands with the selected antennas and frequency extenders for frequencies above 50 GHz. The intermediate frequency bandwidth was set to 1 kHz for all frequency sub-bands. The measurement system was set in a semi-anechoic chamber. Antennas were surrounded by absorbers to minimize potential reflections. The antenna half-power beamwidth (HPBW) was around 20° except for the frequency band [2-30 GHz] where HPBW ranges from 90° to 30°. Antennas and converters were mounted on mechanical rails as illustrated in Figure 4. The transmit antenna is able to move on the x-axis to adjust the distance between the receive and transmit antennas. The receive antenna can move on the Y-Z plane to align the antennas. The distance between both antennas, ranged between 1 m and 1.5 m, is a trade-off as opposite constraints shall be respected. The distance shall be large enough to respect the far-field conditions but not too large to limit the free space loss and therefore increase the maximal measured reflection or transmission losses. The material under test (MUT) was placed at normal incidence between the two antennas within a material holder support. The material

holder is an appropriate support that easily maintains MUTs at normal incidence and minimize possible paths interfering with the direct transmitted signal such as the diffraction on the MUT edges. The material holder is square-shaped with dimensions 1.50m x 1.50m with a square hole of dimensions 50 cm x 50 cm sculpted in its center where the MUT sample is inserted. The side facing the transmitter is filled with absorbers as shown in Figure 4

Figure 4: Measurement system

3.2. Measured materials

Twenty-two different common building materials were measured. They are grouped in Table 3 into categories depending on the material type or function in building. Figure 6 shows material sample pictures. The targeted thickness was 2 cm to be able to resolve internal multipaths while limiting the sample weight for safety and security reasons. Figure 5 illustrates the roughness degrees of the different mortars by zooming the mortar pictures.

Figure 5: Roughness degree of mortars

Category	Material	Thickness d	Description
Glass	Coated glass	6 mm	Energy-efficient glass with a thin metallic film layer on one side to reduce infrared transmission
	Laminated glass	8 mm	Safety unbreakable glass composed by two glass layers stuck together with a thin polymer interlayer
	Patterned glass	4 mm	Glass with decorative patterns
Plasterboard	BA13	13 mm	Standard plasterboard
	BA18	18 mm	Standard plasterboard
Wood and derivatives	Medium Density Fiber (MDF)	22 mm	Compressed wood fibers to a panel format.
	Chipboard	22 mm	Melamine-faced chipboard
	Plywood	22 mm	
Concrete-like materials	Aerated concrete	70 mm	
	Mortar A	22 mm	low roughness surface
	Mortar B	22 mm	Medium low roughness surface
	Mortar C	23 mm	Medium high roughness surface
	Mortar D	24 mm	High roughness surface
Flooring	Vinyl tile	4 mm	
	Ceramic tile	8 mm	
	Office carpet tile	5 mm	
Insulation plates	Polystyrene	20 mm	Glass wool ceiling tiles in office building
	GW20	20 mm	
	GW36	36 mm	
Miscellaneous	Plexiglass	19 mm	
	Gypsum fiberboard (GFB)	18 mm	Composite material with plant fibers and gypsum
	Plastic fiberboard (PFB)	15 mm	Composite material with plant fibers and polymer

Table 3 : List of measured materials with their corresponding thicknesses d

Figure 6: Pictures of measured materials

3.3. Measurement procedure

The VNA S parameters are measured for each frequency band listed in Table 2 according to the following procedure:

1. The corresponding measurement equipment to the selected band is installed and the VNA is configured to the appropriate frequency range. Then, the VNA is calibrated using a standard Trough, Open, Short, Match (TOSM) calibration for below 50 GHz frequency ranges. For above 50 GHz frequency ranges, the frequency converter modules are installed. A simple Short, Offset-short, and load (SOL) calibration is performed as the Through calibration is impossible due to mechanical constraints. The receive and transmit antennas are connected to the measurement equipment after the calibration.
2. The previous calibration is convenient for a quick real-time analysis of S parameters to check the measurement validity but needs to be completed by reference measurements to extract the material reflected and transmitted transfer functions. First, parameters S_{11} and S_{21} are measured in free space by removing the material holder. They are denoted by $S_{11}^{FS}(f)$ and $S_{21}^{FS}(f)$. $S_{11}^{FS}(f)$ allows the estimation of the antenna return loss and $S_{21}^{FS}(f)$ is a reference measurement to estimate transmission losses. Second, the material holder is installed, and a metallic plate considered as a perfect reflector is inserted in the frame as for a MUT. S_{11} is measured and is denoted by $S_{11}^{MET}(f)$. It will be used as a reference to estimate material reflection losses.
3. When reference measurements are completed, slabs are put in the material holder and material measurements are proceeded. The measurement is performed at 3 points separated by 10 cm. The material raw S parameters are denoted by $S_{11}^{Meas}(f)$ and $S_{21}^{Meas}(f)$ for reflection and transmission measurements, respectively. When all material raw measurements are done, another frequency band is selected, and the same procedure is applied again.

3.4. Data processing

$H_r^{MUT}(f)$ and $H_t^{MUT}(f)$ are the intrinsic material reflection and transmission frequency response and $h_r^{MUT}(t)$ and $h_t^{MUT}(t)$ the corresponding complex impulse responses (CIR). $H_r^{MUT}(f)$ and $H_t^{MUT}(f)$ are computed according to (10)

$$H_r^{MUT}(f) = \frac{TG[S_{11}^{Meas}(f) - S_{11}^{FS}(f)]}{TG[S_{11}^{Met}(f) - S_{11}^{FS}(f)]} \quad H_t^{MUT}(f) = \frac{TG[S_{21}^{Meas}(f)]}{TG[S_{21}^{FS}(f)]} \quad (10)$$

$TG[.]$ is the time gating operator which is a temporal filter applied on the inverse Fast Fourier Transform (iFFT) of reference or material S functions. It rejects all undesirable components such as wall reflections or MUT edge diffractions. Subtracting $S_{11}^{FS}(f)$ from $S_{11}^{MET}(f)$ and $S_{11}^{Meas}(f)$ is not mandatory if the distance between the transmit antenna and the MUT is large enough but it makes the time gating for reflection measurement more reliable as it reduces dramatically the potential time overlap of $h_{11}^{FS}(t)$ on $h_{11}^{MUT}(t)$ or $h_{11}^{MET}(t)$. Figure 7 illustrates the effect of the time gating on S_{11} functions for PFB at 30-50 GHz.

The division of time gated measured S functions by time gated reference S functions is a normalization process. It extracts the intrinsic material frequency response by deembedding from the time gated measurement the free space path loss and the equipment frequency response not included in the initial VNA calibration. In the following sections, the data analysis and model comparison will be mainly based on power profile. A *pp* prefix added to a complex vector indicates the power profile of the vector. For instance, $pp_h_r^{MUT}(t)$ is the power profile of $h_r^{MUT}(t)$ and is equal to $10 * \text{Log}_{10}(|h_r^{MUT}(t)|^2)$. The distance scale is computed from the time scale assuming the light speed in vacuum.

Figure 7: Measurement power delay profiles before and after time gating.

4. Permittivity and conductivity estimation

As the measurement presented in this work are complex measurement over very large bandwidths, it is possible to resolve in the time domain the multipath described in the theoretical part. For instance, Figure 8 and Figure 9 show $h_r^{MUT}(t)$ and $h_t^{MUT}(t)$ for BA18 at different frequency ranges. Path 1R, 2R, 1T, 2T can be clearly identified. Consequently, we apply separate estimation methods for the permittivity and conductivity. First, the permittivity is estimated by two different methods based either on the delay or on the amplitude of reflected or transmitted paths. We will only consider path 1R amplitude and path 1T delay as illustrated in Figure 10 because second order paths are often below the noise level at the highest frequencies. The initial measurement sub-bands were slightly rearranged in order to define nine new sub-bands of about 30 GHz bandwidth: [2-30 GHz] numbered 1, [30-50 GHz] numbered 2, [50-75 GHz] numbered 3, [75-110 GHz] numbered 4, [110-140 GHz] numbered 5, [140-170 GHz] numbered 6, [170-200 GHz] numbered 7, [200-230 GHz] numbered 8, [230-260 GHz] numbered 9. An analyzed bandwidth of roughly 30 GHz is a good trade-off to keep a good resolution for the path detection, to consider a constant value for the permittivity and to assess the large-scale frequency dependency of permittivity

Figure 8: $pp_h_r^{MUT}(t)$ for BA18

Figure 9: $pp_h_t^{MUT}(t)$ for BA18

Figure 10: Permittivity estimation method

Method 1 is based on the delay. Let's define t_{P1T} the delay of path 1T. The wave speed inside the material is equal to $\frac{c}{\sqrt{\epsilon_r}}$, c being the wave celerity in vacuum. Then, the relative permittivity ϵ_r is calculated according to (11).

$$\varepsilon_r = \left(\frac{t_{1T} * C}{d} + 1 \right)^2 \quad (11)$$

Method 2 is based on the amplitude. Let's define h_r^{1R} the amplitude of P1R.

$h_r^{1R} = \frac{\sqrt{\varepsilon_r} - 1}{\sqrt{\varepsilon_r} + 1}$, then, ε_r can be calculated as in (12).

$$\varepsilon_r = \left(\frac{1 + h_r^{1R}}{1 - h_r^{1R}} \right)^2 \quad (12)$$

Figure 12 shows permittivities estimated for the plexiglass, mortar and chipboard. The permittivity estimation is sometimes unreliable for rough surface materials, inhomogeneous materials, or multi-layer materials because $h_r^{MUT}(t)$ or $h_t^{MUT}(t)$ are not enough resolved to detect without any ambiguity path 1R or path 1T. For instance and as illustrated in Figure 11, path 1T detection is not straightforward for frequency above 140 GHz, hence the mortar permittivity was not estimated by method 1 above 140 GHz. Permittivities estimated by method 1 and method 2 are similar for most of the materials (e.g. the plexiglass) but diverge for some materials when the frequency increases. We can observe in Figure 12 that the permittivity estimated by method 2 for the mortar decreases artificially due to the scattering. This point is discussed more in details in the next section. We can also observe that the chipboard permittivity estimated by method 2 strongly increases with frequency, whereas the permittivity estimated by method 1 remains constant. The permittivity increase by method 2 is certainly due to the melamine at the chipboard surface but the exact physical explanation is still under investigation and will be presented in a future scientific paper.

Figure 11: $pp_h_t^{MUT}(t)$ for Mortar B

Permittivity values estimated by method 1 are more representative of the material electrical properties and less dependent of the material surface state. Consequently, they are more relevant to assess the permittivity frequency dependency. They are reported in Figure 13, Figure 14 and Figure 15 for various materials. It confirms that the permittivity is independent of the frequency even at frequency above 100 GHz. The final permittivity value reported in Table 4 is averaged over the different frequency bands and both estimation methods when permittivity values are available or meaningful.

Figure 12: Estimation method comparison

Figure 13: Material relative permittivity 1

Figure 14: Material relative permittivity 2

Figure 15: Material relative permittivity 3

The conductivity estimation was not performed by detecting path 1T amplitude for each frequency sub-band as the conductivity decreases with frequency and as the transmission losses are highly impacted by the material inhomogeneity. This point is discussed more in details in the next section. Consequently, a simple and robust approach is to estimate parameters c and d by an iterative approach in order to minimize the error between $pp_H_t^{MUT}(f)$ and $pp_H_t^{ITUF}(f)$. The conductivity is estimated assuming the constant permittivity as indicated hereabove.

5. Comparison between measurement and the ITUF model

$pp_{H_r}^{MUT}(f)$ and $pp_{H_t}^{MUT}(f)$ are shown in figures from Figure 18 to Figure 61 for the different materials. Results are compared to the ITUF model and to the ITU model for materials defined in the ITU model. For clarity reasons and to avoid plot overlap, only path 1T and path 1R are considered for ITU model simulations. The ITUF model error is defined as the difference between $pp_{H_r}^{MUT}(f)$ and $pp_{H_r}^{ITUF}(f)$

A quick visual inspection of material reflection and transmission functions shows that almost all materials follow the ITUF model up to 50 GHz but behave differently for frequencies above 50 GHz. This behavior do not depend on the dielectric properties as it was mentioned in the last section but depends on the material structure. The material could be whether homogeneous or heterogeneous, multi-layered, possessing a smooth or rough surface, etc. This section highlights typical cases when we observe noticeable agreement or differences between measurement and the ITUF model

The ITUF model for the plexiglass agrees very well with $pp_{H_r}^{MUT}(f)$ and $pp_{H_t}^{MUT}(f)$, even at frequencies above 100 GHz. No difference is observed between the three measurement points. Figure 16 and Figure 17 illustrate $pp_{h_r}^{MUT}(t)$ and $pp_{h_t}^{MUT}(t)$ of plexiglass at different frequency bands and put in evidence the source of the periodic oscillation. Paths 1R and 2R can be clearly distinguished. Path 1R amplitude remains constant with the frequency whereas path 2R or 1T amplitude gets smaller as the frequency increases due to the penetration loss. Glass is also a homogeneous material and the conclusions drawn for the plexiglass could be extended to a standard glass. The glass samples selected for the measurement are not standard glass and they illustrate how some variations on the material structure may change the material transmission and reflection responses. $pp_{H_r}^{MUT}(f)$ and $pp_{H_t}^{MUT}(f)$ for the laminated glass exhibit different form of oscillations compared to the ITUF model as shown in Figure 34 and Figure 35. It is due to the two layers structuring the laminated glass. Additional internal reflected paths are created generating new multipath interferences. The coated glass sample was measured by positioning the metallic coating on the opposite side of the transmitter. Due to the presence of the metallic layer on the coated glass, the transmission loss increases by roughly 30 dB compared to a standard glass. The ITUF simulation for the coated glass was performed with the dielectric parameters estimated for the laminated glass. The patterned glass sample was measured by positioning the pattern on the side of the transmitter. $pp_{H_r}^{MUT}(f)$ decreases by 5 dB compared to $pp_{H_r}^{ITUF}(f)$ for frequency above 100 GHz due to the non-flat pattern glass surface. The reflection is no more specular decreasing path 1R amplitude. A similar effect is observed with rough surfaces discussed in the next paragraph.

Figure 16: $pp_{h_r}^{MUT}(t)$ for Plexiglass

Figure 17: $pp_{h_t}^{MUT}(t)$ for Plexiglass

Figure 18: $pp_H_r^{MUT}(f)$ for Mortar A

Figure 19: $pp_H_t^{MUT}(f)$ for Mortar A

Figure 20: $pp_H_r^{MUT}(f)$ for Mortar B

Figure 21: $pp_H_t^{MUT}(f)$ for Mortar B

Figure 22: $pp_H_r^{MUT}(f)$ for Mortar C

Figure 23: $pp_H_t^{MUT}(f)$ for Mortar C

Figure 24: $pp_H_r^{MUT}(f)$ for Mortar D

Figure 25: $pp_H_t^{MUT}(f)$ for Mortar D

Figure 26: $pp_H_r^{MUT}(f)$ for Aerated concrete

Figure 27: $pp_H_t^{MUT}(f)$ for Aerated concrete

Figure 28: $pp_H_r^{MUT}(f)$ for BA 13

Figure 29: $pp_H_t^{MUT}(f)$ for BA 13

Figure 30: $pp_H_r^{MUT}(f)$ for BA 18

Figure 31: $pp_H_t^{MUT}(f)$ for BA 18

Figure 32: $pp_H_r^{MUT}(f)$ for GFB

Figure 33: $pp_H_t^{MUT}(f)$ for GFB

Figure 34: $pp_H_r^{MUT}(f)$ for Laminated glass

Figure 35: $pp_H_t^{MUT}(f)$ for Laminated glass

Figure 36: $pp_H_r^{MUT}(f)$ for Coated glass

Figure 37: $pp_H_t^{MUT}(f)$ for Coated glass

Figure 38: $pp_H_r^{MUT}(f)$ for Patterned glass

Figure 39: $pp_H_t^{MUT}(f)$ for Patterned glass

Figure 40: $pp_H_r^{MUT}(f)$ for Plexiglass

Figure 41: $pp_H_t^{MUT}(f)$ for Plexiglass

Figure 42: $pp_H_r^{MUT}(f)$ for Glass wool 20

Figure 43: $pp_H_t^{MUT}(f)$ for Glass wool 20

Figure 44: $pp_H_r^{MUT}(f)$ for Glass wool 38

Figure 45: $pp_H_t^{MUT}(f)$ for Glass wool 38

Figure 46: $pp_H_r^{MUT}(f)$ for Polystyrene

Figure 47: $pp_H_t^{MUT}(f)$ for polystyrene

Figure 48: $pp_H_r^{MUT}(f)$ for PFB

Figure 49: $pp_H_t^{MUT}(f)$ for PFB

Figure 50: $pp_H_r^{MUT}(f)$ for Vinyl

Figure 51: $pp_H_t^{MUT}(f)$ for Vinyl

Figure 52: $pp_H_r^{MUT}(f)$ for Ceramic

Figure 53: $pp_H_t^{MUT}(f)$ for Ceramic

Figure 54: $pp_H_r^{MUT}(f)$ for Carpet

Figure 55: $pp_H_t^{MUT}(f)$ for Carpet

Figure 56: $pp_H_r^{MUT}(f)$ for Chipboard

Figure 57: $pp_H_t^{MUT}(f)$ for Chipboard

Figure 58: $pp_H_r^{MUT}(f)$ for MDF

Figure 59: $pp_H_t^{MUT}(f)$ for MDF

Figure 60: $pp_H_r^{MUT}(f)$ for Plywood

Figure 61: $pp_H_t^{MUT}(f)$ for Plywood

The mortar family illustrates the scattering impact on the ITUF performance. We clearly observe in Figure 18, Figure 20, Figure 22 and Figure 24 that the regular periodic small-scale fading disappears at a threshold frequency and is replaced by an irregular fading with no correlation between the three points. This effect is due to the scattering on the surface. The fading is no more due to the complex recombination between path 1R and path 2R but is due to the complex recombination of scattered components. The scattering increases the reflection loss value and makes the ITUF model inaccurate. The threshold frequency and the ITUF model error depends on the roughness degree. For mortar A, the threshold frequency is around 50 GHz and the model error is less than -3 dB. For mortar D, the threshold frequency is around 20 GHz and the model error is around -10 dB with maximal values at -20 dB. Additional reflection measurements with 40° HPBW antennas instead of the initial 20° HPBW antennas were performed between 170 and 260 GHz to confirm the scattering effect. Results are shown in Figure 62. $pp_H_r^{MUT}(f)$ for the plexiglass is considered as the reference with no scattering as path 1R and 2R are the only received paths and $pp_H_r^{MUT}(f)$ does not change with the antenna angular aperture. In case of mortar C, secondary paths appear beside the main peak due to the scattering. This effect is enhanced using the antenna with the 40° HPBW. The larger the antenna angular aperture, the larger the illuminated area on the MUT surface, the higher the number of received scattered components.

Figure 62: Impact of the antenna angular aperture on $pp_H_r^{MUT}(t)$

We also observed for some materials such as chipboard, MDF, PFB or glasswool that $pp_H_r^{MUT}(f)$ increases with frequency. The melamine chipboard is the most typical example with an increase of 7 dB at 260 GHz compared to the ITUF model. No obvious reason was found to explain this behavior. It might be explained by the specific structure of these materials composed by fibers or small wood particles. Fibers or small particles likely behave as good reflectors when the wavelength decreases. Regarding chipboard, the melamine layer on the chipboard surface may also explain the increase of $pp_H_r^{MUT}(f)$ with frequency. New measurements would be required to investigate more in details the reflection loss of composite materials or covered material (melamine, wallpaper, painting, varnish, etc).

For some materials and especially for MDF and PFB, permittivity values estimated by method 1 and method 2 did not give the same results. For instance, the MDF relative permittivity is equal to 2 and 2.9 with method 1 and 2 respectively. The final value reported in Table 4 is the average and equal to 2.4. It explains why the ITUF model seems to be incorrectly fitted on the measurement.

Material transmission losses are well modeled by the ITUF model “on average” as the conductivity was estimated to minimize the difference between $pp_H_t^{MUT}(f)$ and $pp_H_t^{ITUF}(f)$. But the ITUF model error varies significantly depending on the frequency and the material heterogeneity. For instance mortars, plasterboards, composite materials or wood materials transmission functions agrees with the ITUF model up to 50 GHz, but some variations appear above 50 GHz. The model error is about +/- 5 dB but can exceed +/- 10 dB, and the three points results are uncorrelated. Similarly to what have been observed for the reflection losses, secondary paths appear beside path 1T when frequency increases as illustrated in Figure 11. The multipath interference generates a small-scale fading explaining the errors between the model and the measurement. As these multipaths mainly appear with non-homogeneous materials, it suggests that a volumic scattered component inside the material is created due to the material inhomogeneity. This

diffuse component become dominant over the specular transmission component in the case of mortars when the gravel size is comparable to the wavelength. It modifies the transmission gain slope making the ITUF model unsuitable. For instance, the slope break is observed at 100 GHz for mortar C in Figure 23

Similarly to reflection measurements, additional transmission measurements with 40° HPBW antennas instead of the initial 20° HPBW antennas were performed between 170 and 260 GHz to confirm the volumic scattering effect. Results are shown in Figure 63 for the glasswool and mortar C. Observations from this figure are very similar to those mentioned for the reflexion. The $pp_h_t^{MUT}(t)$ length is increased when using larger angular aperture antennas.

Figure 63: Impact of the antenna angular aperture on $pp_H_t^{MUT}(t)$

In contrast to homogeneous smooth surface materials such as the glass or the plexiglass, transmission or reflection frequency functions of many materials show some frequency discontinuities between the frequency sub-bands. The reason for these discontinuities is the material heterogeneity or rough surfaces jointly with the material positioning accuracy. The material holder was removed and repositioned between two consecutive frequency sub-band measurements to perform the reference measurements. Even though particular attention have been paid on the material holder accurate positioning, materials were not illuminated exactly at the same point for all the sub-bands explaining the discontinuities hereabove mentioned.

Other noticeable behaviors are observed for some specific materials. Aerial concrete transmission results are unexpected. Aerial concrete looks like a concrete foam and would be classified as an heterogeneous material after a first visual inspection, but $pp_H_t^{MUT}(f)$ exhibits a regular decrease with frequency without any small-scale variations (Figure 25). Plywood is a typical multi-layer material. $pp_H_r^{MUT}(f)$ presents for frequency above 20 GHz irregular oscillations that are due to the multiple internal reflections from the different wood layers as illustrated in Figure 60. Multipath interferences create deep small-scale fading but do not increase the average reflection loss. Finally, polystyrene is known to be transparent to EM at cmW frequencies. Results shown in Figure 46 confirm this property even at frequencies up to 260 GHz.

6. ITU model validation above 100 GHz

The estimated permittivity and conductivity are reported in Table 4 and compared with the ITU model values when available. For people more familiar with link budget and less familiar with physical metrics such as the permittivity and conductivity values, Figure 64, Figure 65, Figure 66 and Figure 67 help the understanding of Table 4. Figure 64 plots the reflection gain r described in 2.1 versus the relative permittivity at normal incidence. Figure 65, Figure 66 and Figure 67 provides the attenuation rate according the ITUF conductivities reported in Table 4. There is a good agreement between the experimental permittivity values and those provided by ITU. Consequently, we can extend the permittivity ITU model for frequencies up to 300 GHz. But many building materials are composite or multi-layered materials. When the wavelength decreases, these materials cannot still be considered as homogeneous with flat surface, and the reflection loss may be incorrectly modeled by the permittivity-dependent Fresnel equations. Applying scattering models or a multi-layered model is one option but this option is complex to implement in ray tracing, increases the processing time and makes more complicated the digital map description. Above 100 GHz, a simple model evolution would be to define correction factors to take into account the reflection loss decrease or increase compared to the model. This approach would require new measurements to investigate more in details the reflection loss of composite materials or covered material (melamine, wallpaper, painting, varnish, etc).

Estimated parameters c and d are in agreement with those given by the ITU for the glass and plywood but are sometimes very different. For instance, we never found d values less than 1. It implies that the ITU model underestimates the penetration loss at high frequencies for materials having a d value less than 1. Figure 19, Figure 21, Figure 23, Figure 25 and Figure 57 illustrates the model error for the chipboard and mortars. The recommendation is to consider the dielectric parameters fitted by our measurement at least for the mortar and chipboard. Regarding the transmission loss variation around the model due to the inhomogeneity at high frequencies, the ITU model could be improved by adding to $H_t^{ModITU}(f)$ a statistical variable but as indicated hereabove for the reflection loss, this approach requires additional measurements to determine reliable statistics.

Table 4: Estimated and ITU permittivity and conductivity

Category	Material	ITU name	Relative permittivity ϵ_r		Conductivity σ (S/m)			
			ITUF model	ITU model	ITUF model		ITU model	
					c	D	c	D
Glass	Laminated glass	Glass	6.2	6.27	0.005	1.2	0.0043	1.1925
Plasterboard	BA13	Plasterboard	2.5	2.94	0.0004	1.35	0.0116	0.7076
	BA18		2.9		0.0004	1.4		
Wood and derivatives	MDF		2.4	NA	0.006	1.0	NA	NA
	Plywood	Wood	2	1.99	0.007	1.0	0.0047	1.0718
	Chipboard	Chipboard	2.4	2.58	0.007	1.1	0.0217	0.78
Concrete-like materials	Aerated concrete	NA	1.9	NA	0.002	1.3	NA	NA
	Mortar B	Concrete	4.6	5.31	0.002	1.5	0.0326	0.8095
	Mortar C		6.4		0.004	1.4		
Flooring	Vinyl	NA	3.8	NA	0.0002	1.6	NA	NA
	Ceramic	NA	5.9	NA	0.005	1.2	NA	NA
	Office carpet	NA	2.5	NA	0.005	1.05	NA	NA
Insulation plates	Polystyrene	NA	1.05	NA	0.000008	1.1	NA	NA
	GW 20	Ceiling board	1.25	1.5	0.0002	1.35	0.0005	1.1634
	GW 36		1.2	1.5	0.002	1.2		
Miscellaneous	Plexiglass	NA	2.65	NA	0.0001	1.5	NA	NA
	GFB	NA	3.5	NA	0.002	1.25	NA	NA
	PFB	NA	2.3	NA	0.0001	1.55	NA	NA

The analysis shows that the ITU model needs to be improved for frequencies above 100 GHz by considering the material surface state or the volume inhomogeneity for the reflection and transmission coefficient processing. But as

a first step, the ITU model could be used as it is in many simulations related to 6G sub-THz scenarios. Reflection loss errors due to rough surfaces may be not a concern in office environment, shopping mall, airport, etc as most of the material are quite smooth. Transmission loss errors due to the material inhomogeneity may be not a concern as they concern high transmission losses at high frequencies. Simulating a transmission error of 20 dB instead of 30 dB may not significantly impact system simulation if we consider that a transmission loss higher than 20 dB corresponds to a blockage.

Figure 64: Reflection gain vs relative permittivity

Figure 65: Attenuation rate 1

Figure 66: Attenuation rate 2

Figure 67: Attenuation rate 3

7. Conclusion

Reflection and transmission measurement results from 2 to 260 GHz for 22 different building materials were presented in this paper. Related permittivity and conductivity were estimated and compared to the ITU-R P.2040 model. Following key findings valid on the measurement frequency range can be drawn from the data analysis:

- The permittivity is independent of the frequency and the ITU model values can be extended to 300 GHz
- The conductivity increases with the frequency and the ITU generic function $\sigma = cf^d$ can be extended to 300 GHz. But fitted parameters c and d are for some materials very different from those proposed by the ITU. The use of fitted parameters c and d provided in this document are recommended
- Above 50 GHz, the material surface roughness and volume heterogeneity create scatterer multipaths that generate a frequential small-scale fading on the transmission or reflection transfer functions. The average reflection loss is also increased in case of rough surfaces. The additional transmission or reflection losses due to the scattering depends on the frequency and may exceed 10 dB above 100 GHz

The paper highlights the impact of scattering on the reflection loss in case of rough or relief surfaces. It may explain why some papers conclude that the propagation channel contains less paths in the propagation channel at sub-THz frequencies. Nevertheless, sub-THz wireless system target more an indoor environment where wall or object surfaces are generally flat and smooth. It can be assumed that the specular reflected component will remain predominant compared to scattered components. This assumption needs to be confirmed by additional measurements on multi-layer, composite or covered materials in a real environment

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